

Ultrafast Soliton Pulse Compression and Delivery in Hollow-Core Fiber

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We investigate soliton self-compression in gas-filled hollow-core fiber, with particular emphasis on practicalities related to realizing real-world applications. To demonstrate an effective balance of compression ratio and pulse quality we present an optimally-designed neon-filled anti-resonant hollow-core fiber which achieves six-fold compression to 45.6 fs and a pulse quality factor of 0.82. This system demonstrates excellent resilience against power fluctuations with a decrease in pulse duration of just 13.5 % for a power increase of 25 %. Furthermore, we investigate the robustness of compression against bending, since many applications benefit from the flexible delivery properties of fiber. We observe impressive bend resilience when employing an argon-filled polarization-maintaining anti-resonant fiber. As the fiber bend radius is reduced from 130 mm to 60 mm the compressed pulse duration of 57.9 fs increased by just 4 %, whilst the polarization extinction ratio is maintained above 10 dB. Simulations and results on energy scaling and lifetime will be presented.

Laser systems delivering high average power and high-quality ultrafast pulses with durations of several-hundred femtoseconds are beneficial for numerous applications [1]. However, certain applications including materials processing [2] and those within medicine such as ophthalmology [3] would benefit from even shorter durations, i.e., < 100 fs, whilst maintaining sufficient pulse quality. Furthermore, simple and flexible control of the spatial position of the laser beam can be advantageous, particularly when the target is difficult to access. Gas-filled hollow-core fiber (HCF) offers a platform to meet the needs of these two practical requirements. This remarkable architecture allows fine control of the nonlinearity and dispersion landscape through variation of gas species, pressure, core diameter and interaction length. Thus, with defined input pulse parameters, soliton self-compression can result in a specific pulse compression ratio (CR) and pulse quality factor (QF) subject to soliton scaling rules [4]. Combining this with their excellent power handling capabilities and inherent physical flexibility suggests that HCF could be the ultimate solution for compressing ultrafast pulses whilst simultaneously allowing control over the spatial position of the laser beam. In this work we present an investigation into the suitability of HCF in providing both compression and delivery functionality.

Firstly, we demonstrate a regime which can achieve an effective CR whilst maintaining a high QF. Generally, QF decreases as CR increases [4], and it is therefore particularly important to consider the balance of these effects when designing a compression system for applications which cannot tolerate low pulse quality. To demonstrate this balance, we compress 275 fs pulses at 10 MHz from a 1033 nm mode-locked system. To determine the optimal operating conditions for both a high CR and QF we performed simulations based on a split-step Fourier method for solving the non-linear Schrödinger equation. Based on these simulations we opted for a soliton number of $N \sim 2.7$, experimentally achieved with 7.5 m of 27 μm core diameter anti-resonant (AR) HCF filled with neon at 9.8 bar to achieve optimal compression at the fiber output (set-up in Fig. 1 (d)). At the maximum available input power of 10 W we obtained an output power of 7.12 W (712 nJ pulse energy), a pulse duration of 45.6 fs (Fig. 1 (b)) which corresponds to $CF = 6$ and $QF = 0.82$. As depicted in Fig. 1 (a), the output pulse duration was robust against changes in pulse energy, with an increase in input pulse energy from 800 nJ to 1000 nJ (25 %) corresponding to a slight decrease in pulse duration from 52.7 fs to 45.6 fs (13.5 %). This is encouraging since the expected energy variations in practical applications would be significantly lower. The compressed pulse had a linear polarization state with a polarization extinction ratio (PER) > 22 dB.

To investigate the robustness of pulse compression against bending we employed a 27 μm core diameter polarization-maintaining (PM) AR HCF. The PM nature gives a stronger resilience against external perturbations for radiation aligned along the birefringence axes. Initially a 3 m fiber length was filled with argon at 2.6 bar and placed on a horizontal surface, arranged in coils with bend radii of 130 mm. We launched pulses as above and aligned to a birefringence axis of the fiber. For an input pulse energy of 610 nJ we obtained compression to 57.9 fs ($CF = 4.75$), $QF = 0.7$, $PER = 12.5$ dB and output pulse energy of 440 nJ. A single coil

was manipulated to form an oblong shape (Fig. 1 (e)) to reduce the bend radius, whilst the pulse duration and PER were monitored. For a reduction in bend radius from 130 mm to 60 mm the pulse duration only increased by 4 % to 60.3 fs, whilst the PER decreased slightly and was maintained just above 10 dB (Fig. 1 (e)). These results indicate practical usability, since the duration and PER variation with bend radii are relatively small, and the bend radii tested are already on the shorter side for what an armored fiber cable could achieve in practice. The fiber was further manipulated into a figure-of-eight shape (Fig. 1 (e)) both without and with a twist in the fiber. Without a twist, and with a bend radius of 40 mm, the pulse duration increased to 65.2 fs and the PER was reduced to 7.8 dB indicating a noticeable degradation in performance. However, the degradation is far more severe when a twist was incorporated, where for a bend radius of 50 mm the pulse degradation increased to 67.5 fs and the PER reduced drastically to 2.2 dB (diamond markers in Fig. 1 (e)). This indicates that twists in the fiber are very detrimental to performance. Finally, the initial coil arrangement was rotated by 90 degrees to a vertical position, for which the performance was largely unchanged (triangle markers in Fig. 1 (e)). Further to the discussion above we will present results on pulse energy scaling and lifetime performance.

Figure 1: Compressed pulse duration as a function of output pulse energy in a neon-filled AR HCF (a), the retrieved FROG temporal pulse profile at maximum output power (b), measured and retrieved FROG traces at maximum output power (c), experimental set-up (d), compressed pulse duration and PER as a function of bend radii, r , of argon-filled PM AR HCF with bending arrangements (e).

1. <https://www.nktphotonics.com/products/ultrafast-fiber-lasers/aeropulse-fs-50/>
2. R. Gattass, E. Mazur, "Femtosecond laser micromachining in transparent materials," *Nature Photon* **2**, 219–225 (2008)
3. B. Pajic, et al, "Why Use Ultrashort Pulses in Ophthalmology and Which Factors Affect Cut Quality," *Medicina* **7** (2021)
4. D. Schade, et al, "Scaling rules for high quality soliton self-compression in hollow-core fibers," *Opt. Express* **29**, 19147–19158 (2021)